

THE CHALLENGES STUDENTS MAY FACE IN ACADEMIC WRITING

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Abstract. *In higher education, writing has been seen as a significant and essential component of the learning process. Proficiency in essay writing paves the path for success in more complex assignments, such as research papers, reports, summaries, and academic articles. Students with strong writing skills can therefore perform better academically and have greater opportunities to land important jobs.*

Keywords: *higher education, academic writing, research papers, writing skills, literary skills, equivocality.*

Writing has always been regarded as an important and necessary part of the educational process in higher education, and as I currently work at the University of World Economy and Diplomacy in Tashkent, helping students improve their writing abilities is my primary goal. Proficiency in essay writing prepares one for success in more challenging projects, such as research papers, academic articles, reports, and summaries. As a result, young people with strong writing skills can do better academically and have more chances of obtaining jobs of significance. Writing instruction is one of the most challenging things a teacher can do. The goals and tenets of academic essay writing have been covered in this article by providing discipline-specific advice and techniques. Together with a thorough description of how to create and express ideas in a genuine and convincing manner, there is also a reflection on how the learners embraced these tools and how it could enable me to instruct my students in this particular field.

The IOWA State University-provided Developing and Teaching Academic Writing 64 online teacher training course in 2023 gave me the opportunity to learn more about academic writing and how to create lessons that will satisfy the writing needs of my students.

Then, over my fifteen years as a teacher, I encountered several significant difficulties in instructing academic writing. I will thus share some of my observations with you in addition to explaining all of my experiences. In addition, I agree with the notion that academic writing entails both hard reading and writing. Additionally, we will surely encounter a variety of challenges related to teaching academic writing during our professional teaching careers. Given the close relationship between writing and reading, this is accurate. Also, as most students struggle because they haven't had enough practice, I would add theoretical and practical training as well.

Despite the fact that academic writing comes with a number of challenges, my main concerns are producing research papers, articles, summaries, essays, and reports. A lot of students have trouble paraphrasing and avoiding plagiarism. They are incapable of crafting strong thesis statements and topic sentences.

Moreover, this is a great chance to learn more about academic writing and how to write academic articles that meet my students' writing needs through the Writing Across Boundaries program. Because of the nature of the program, I think it would provide me the chance to continue to be a catalyst in my community and within higher education. Also, I would be able to

deepen my grasp of how to create research papers, reports, summaries, and articles that live up to student standards thanks to this program.

In today's educational system, innovative methods are gaining popularity. A cascading approach is one of these methods. Working together with other researchers and sharing part of your knowledge are essential. Knowledgeable academics can share their expertise with highly experienced ones by introducing them to new ideas. When you explain anything new, you are forced to reorganize your knowledge and think about it more deeply. In addition, it points out concepts you need to make clearer or areas you need to work on.

Through the Writing Across Boundaries program, I really hope to have the chance to contribute significantly to the academic community, build strong relationships with colleagues in the same field, close the gap between theory and practice, and investigate different methods for putting research findings into practice.

Writing has been considered as a profound and an integral part of learning process in Higher education. Ability to write essays correctly lays an effective way in gaining success in more sophisticated assignments like writing academic articles, reports, summaries and research papers. As a result, students who are good at writing can achieve better results in academic performance and have more privileges in getting prestigious job places.

Quite often, students, having not coped with the essay, begin to think that they simply do not have a gift for writing. However, an academic essay is a genre with certain rules, and therefore writing a good essay involves more not a talent, but a discipline of the mind. In addition, academic essays are a fundamentally scalable genre. That is why, in some academic traditions, an essay is a key element of the educational process: essays are written every week, because having learned how to make an essay for five paragraphs, you understand how you can adapt this knowledge for a term paper, article or dissertation.

According to Smith (1998), writing a good essay is difficult at times, but definitely not impossible. Therefore, it is high time to make some changes in educational system and teach learners to write essays from their early age and apply essay writing in different subjects.

Students of Higher Educational Institutions have to deal with writing during the whole period of learning process. As Anne Whitaker says (2009): “Academic writing is, essentially, the writing you have to do for your university courses.” Your instructors may have different names for academic writing assignments (essay, paper, research paper, term paper, argumentative paper/essay, analysis paper/essay, informative essay, position paper), but all of these assignments have the same goal and principles. In early courses students are obligatory to write academic essays, further they write more complex piece of writings like reports, article reviews, summaries which demand mastering writing skills.

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